

Studying tomato brown rugose fruit virus longevity in soil and virion susceptibility to pH treatments helped improve virus control by soil disinfection

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Fig. S1 Ionic strength of pH-modified ToBRFV virion and virion RNA solutions

Plant and Soil

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Fig. S2 Soil disinfection experimental flow chart

